

Compact devices for the characterization of retarders based on a common-path interferometer

Ines Diaz-Garcia^a, Jesus del Hoyo^{a,*}, Joaquin Andres-Porras^a, Angela Soria-Garcia^a,
Mahmoud H. Elshorbagy^{b,c}, Javier Alda^b, Luis Miguel Sanchez-Brea^a

^a*Applied Optics Complutense Group, Optics Department, Faculty of Physics, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Plaza de las Ciencias, 1, 28040, Madrid, Spain*

^b*Applied Optics Complutense Group, Optics Department, Faculty of Optics and Optometry, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, C/ Arcos de Jalón, 118, 28037, Madrid, Spain*

^c*Physics Department, Faculty of Science, Minia University, El Minia, 61519, Egypt*

Abstract

Interferometry has been proven accurate for measuring the absolute retardance and azimuth of optical retarders, with the additional advantage over previous devices of not requiring the use of additional characterized retarders in the measurement process, but only linear polarizers. Retarder parameters are calculated from the fringe pattern displacement produced by the retarder rotation. In this work, we propose a common optical path configuration for removing interferometric instabilities. We have developed two devices, one based on a double slit, each one with a different linear polarizer (0° and 90°) and another based on a Wollaston prism. We also developed a procedure to remove the additional shift produced by tilted or non-plane-parallel retarders on the fringe pattern upon rotation. First, we have analyzed the effect of using imperfect polarizers in the measurement process using numerical simulations. Then, we experimentally characterized several retarders using both interferometers, obtaining fit errors below 0.1° and repeatabilities down to 0.3° . We also characterized a liquid crystal variable retarder using the Wollaston prism interferometer. In both cases, we compared our results with Mueller polarimetry, obtaining good agreement.

1. Introduction

An accurate characterization of optical retarders is crucial for numerous experiments and devices such as biological tests, optical communications, optical microscopy, spectral

*optbrea@ucm.es

analysis and so forth [1, 2, 3, 4]. Also, they are used in polarimetry for both measuring the polarization properties of a sample or the polarization state of a light source [5, 6]. Some techniques based on rotating polarizers, spectroscopy, nonlinear optical methods, etc. have been proposed to obtain the retardance and azimuth of the fast axis of the retarders with accuracy [7]. A simple method consists of placing and rotating the optical retarder to be characterized between two fixed polarizers with their transmission axis perpendicular to each other. The retardance and fast axis azimuth are determined from the variations of the transmitted intensity [8, 9]. However, this procedure does not allow to distinguish between the fast and slow axis. Xie et al. used amplitude division to characterize the retarder [10], but it requires two quarter waveplates and several Wollaston prisms and intensity detectors, and requires a very precise characterization of setup elements. Other procedures are founded on the interferometry principle. Nakadate [11] used a Young interferometer, Vargas et al. [12] a Fabri-Perot interferometer, and Schnoor et al. [13] a Sagnac interferometer to determine the retardance of retarders when the fast axis azimuth is known. Ming et al. used a heterodyne interferometric technique for measuring both the retardance and fast axis azimuth of the retarder [14]. Later, Chen et al. [15] used a Mach-Zehnder interferometer for the same purpose. Nevertheless, the first procedure requires a very stable laser and the second is very sensitive to vibrations and temperature variations. These mechanical and stability limitations are present in previous methodologies. Moreover, Litwin et al. [16] presented a method of measuring the retardance of waveplates by a continuous phase registration and across the visible spectrum. Nevertheless, to employ this technique, it is necessary to use a variable wavelength light source and to previously know the azimuth of the fast axis.

In [17] we proposed an experimental device based on a Michelson interferometer that allows to simultaneously obtain the retardance and azimuth of the retarders. It consists of a common-path interferometer in which the retarder rotation produces a displacement of interferometric fringes. The fringe displacement is related to the the retarder parameters according to

$$\Phi_m(\theta) = -\arctan\left(\frac{\sin\Delta\cos[2(\theta-\theta_0)]}{\cos\Delta\cos^2[2(\theta-\theta_0)]+\sin^2[2(\theta-\theta_0)]}\right) + \Phi_0, \quad (1)$$

where Φ_m is the phase displacement produced by the rotation of the retarder, Δ is the retardance of the retarder, θ is the rotation angle in the mount reference system, θ_0 is the angle in the mount reference system where the fast axis azimuth corresponds to 0° in the lab reference system so $\theta - \theta_0$ is the fast axis azimuth in the lab reference system, and Φ_0 represents the arbitrary phase origin. The retardance can be obtained from Eq. 1 as the difference between the maximum and minimum phase shift divided by two, $\Delta = (\Phi_{\max} - \Phi_{\min})/2$, as shown in Fig. 1. In addition, the azimuth is obtained as the angle of the motor where the phase shift is minimum, $\theta_0 = \operatorname{argmin}[\Phi_m(\theta)]$. Both parameters can also be obtained by fitting Eq. 1 with Φ_0 , Δ and θ_0 as fit parameters.

Figure 1: (a) Proposed methodology for obtaining the retardance and azimuth of the sample once the phase displacement is experimentally obtained. 2Δ is the double of the retardance and θ_0 is the mount angle where the minimum shift is located. For this example, $\Delta = 90^\circ$ and $\theta_0 = 90^\circ$. (b) General scheme of interference phenomenon.

However, Michelson interferometer experiment presented some drawbacks. Small variations in air and pressure produce a variation in the refractive index of air. Then, as Michelson interferometer arms are separated spatially, these variations produce shifts in the pattern. These variations are slow in time, so its effect can be minimized by reducing the number of measurements but not completely overcome. Also, when the interferometer is not adjusted so both arms have exactly the same length, tiny variations in the illumination wavelength also produce a shift in the pattern. These variations may be produced by a variation in LED temperature or variation in the dominating longitudinal mode of lasers.

In this work, we have developed two different common-path interferometers that do not present these drawbacks: one based on a double-slit and another on a Wollaston prism. As both of them are common-path, air refractive index variations affect both arms almost identically, so no shift is produced. Also, common-path interferometers have the same arm length, so wavelength variations affect only the fringes period but do not produce any shift.

Double slit interferometers have been commonly used for different interferometric applications. Walborn et al. proposed a quantum eraser based on the interference from a double slit [18]. Later, Wu et. al used several double slit interferometers together with imaging sensors to reconstruct non-axisymmetric temperature fields [19]. In particular, Nakadate used a Young interferometer to determine the retardance of retarders [11]. Wollaston prisms have also been used for polarimetry. Williams et al. developed a polarimeter based on a Wollaston beam-splitter polarizer [20]. Later, Xie et al. used three Wollaston prisms and a complex optical system to characterize retarders [10]. Also, Litwin et al. used a device based on a Wollaston prism to spectrally determine the retardance of retarders.

Since the measurement process is based on the fringe displacement, we have identified an additional drawback consisting on the existence of an additional fringe pattern displacement

Figure 2: Deviation of the beam due to the fact that the retarder (orange element) (a) is not perpendicular to the optical axis or (b) its facets are not plano-parallel.

when the optical retarder is not perfectly placed perpendicular to the optical axis or its facets are not plano-parallel, as we show in Fig. 2. This additional displacement, Φ_{tilt} , is periodical over 2π . Then, when performing the experiment, the displacement measured is $\Phi = \Phi_m + \Phi_{\text{tilt}}$. As a consequence, this displacement must be independently measured to correctly characterize the retarder. The process is described in Section 3. In the case of the Wollaston prism interferometer, we developed an experimental setup to measure it at the same time as the main experiment, avoiding the need to perform two different measurements.

Summarizing, we present two new devices for characterizing retarders based on a common-path interferometer, one of them consisting of a double-slit and the other of a Wollaston prism. In Section 2, we carry out an analysis of the experimental system together with the study of its tolerances by numerical simulations. We present the experimental setups that we have developed and the measurement and data processing process in Section 3. We show in Section 4 the experimental results of the characterization of different optical retarders and a liquid crystal using both interferometers. These results are compared with Mueller polarimetry for validation [5].

2. Simulations

The mathematical description of the the proposed double-slit and Wollaston devices is the same to that of the Michelson interferometer [17], as they are based on optical path

differences. As a consequence, Eq. 1 is still valid to determine the fringe pattern for the ideal case. Nevertheless a complete description of the performance for a real device produce very complex equations. As a consequence, we performed numerical simulations, using the open source Python library Py-pol, to determine the capabilities of the device and its tolerances [21]. We tested the influence of using real optical elements. Particularly, we varied the value of the maximum and minimum field transmission coefficients (p_1, p_2) and the retardance of the polarizers (Δ_p). We also tested the influence of experimental errors like using different light source ellipticity angle. Then, the phase displacement is calculated as described in the previous section. As an example, Fig. 3 shows a graphical comparison between an ideal ($p_1 = 1, p_2 = 0$) and non-ideal case ($p_1 = 1, p_2 = 0.06$) for a theoretical retarder with $\Delta = 120^\circ$ and $\theta_0 = 90^\circ$. The dotted red line represents the simulated displacement while the blue line represents fit to Eq. 1. The simulated data perfectly fit the theoretical curve when optical elements are ideal. On the other hand, when polarizers and the light source are not perfect, the matching is not perfect. This is better observed in the residuals graph, calculated as the difference between the modeled and simulated curve. The error for the ideal case is $\Delta\Phi = \pm 0.05^\circ$ and for the real case is $\Delta\Phi = \pm 10^\circ$, the latter being increased due to the remarkable mismatch in the maximums, minimums and inflection points. The standard deviation for each is case is $\sigma = 0.05^\circ$ and $\sigma = 5.98^\circ$, respectively. Considering these interpretations of the simulation, we obtained the fit results of $\Delta^{\text{fit}} = 120.01^\circ$ and $\theta_0^{\text{fit}} = 90.00^\circ$ for ideal conditions, which is a very good agreement, and $\Delta^{\text{fit}} = 130.39^\circ$ and $\theta_0^{\text{fit}} = 91.19^\circ$ for non-ideal conditions, which poses a great deviation from the real values.

We carried out an analysis of the tolerances of the system by measuring the difference between the nominal parameter and the calculated one. For that purpose, we considered two different deviations from the ideal case:

- Polarizers with $p_1 = 1, p_2 \in [0, 0.1]$ and $\Delta_p \in [0, 360^\circ]$.
- A retarder presenting a small diattenuation with $p_1 = 1$ and $p_2 \in [0.9, 1]$.

We calculated displacement of the fringes pattern for different values of Δ, Δ_p and p_2/p_1 , with $p_1 = 1$ and $\theta_0 = 90^\circ$. Then, we calculated the apparent retardance Δ^{fit} and azimuth θ_0^{fit} . Finally, we calculated the errors as the difference between the apparent and the real values. Fig. 4 shows the retardance error for imperfect polarizers distributed throughout all the experimental setup. The error oscillates in a range of almost up to 30° depending on the polarizer parameters. This shows that it is important that the polarizers present a very low minimum transmission and it is preferable to employ polarizers of $\Delta = 90^\circ$ or 270° to accurately determine Δ . From this simulation, we also deduced that the phase displacement maxima and minima position do not vary, so $\theta_0^{\text{fit}} \approx 90.00^\circ$ in all cases

We have also analyzed the case of perfect polarizers but introducing diattenuation in the retarder for materials which accompany birefringence with dichroism. The retardance

Figure 3: Simulation of the phase displacement of a 120° retardance waveplate when considering (a) ideal optical elements and (b) real optical elements. For the latter case, the ellipticity of the light source is $\chi = 15^\circ$, polarizers possess $p_1 = 0.74$, $p_2 = 0.06$ and $\Delta_p = 180^\circ$ and the sample retarders presents $p_1 = p_2 = 0.74$. The red dots describe the simulated behavior of the phase and the one that would be expected. The blue line represents the result obtained with Eq. 1.

Figure 4: Error in retardance estimation when the ratio p_2/p_1 of the polarizer is not null and Δ of the polarizers is in the range from 0° to 360° .

Figure 5: Error in the determination of the retardance when the retarder presents diattenuation and perfect polarizers.

error is shown in Fig. 5. We used several retardance values in the range from 1° to 179° , avoiding 0° and 180° because these are extreme values difficult to simulate and measure. The retardance error is negligible except for $\Delta > 135^\circ$, and severely increases for $\Delta \approx 180^\circ$. The error does not reach exactly a null value for $p_2 = 1$ due to numerical error in the calculation procedure, as shown in the beginning of this section. The variation of the azimuth is negligible in all cases, lower than 0.003° .

3. Experimental setup and procedure

We used two experimental setups. The first one is based on a double slit with polarizers as shown in Fig. 6a. A collimated laser beam, whose wavelength is $\lambda = 639 \text{ nm}$, passes through a polarizer (P) to control the amount of power entering the optical system and avoid the saturation of the camera. Then, a polarizer oriented at 45° (P_{45°) is used to set the polarization to 45° so the output intensity of both slits is equal. Afterwards, the Young double slit presents two polarizers, one for each slit, with orthogonal polarization axis (P_{0° , P_{90°). Then, the sample retarder (Q) is placed on a motorized rotation stage (M). Finally, the interference fringes are generated in the focal plane of a lens, using a polarizer oriented at 45° ($P_{45^\circ}^\alpha$ and $P_{45^\circ}^\beta$). The camera is placed in the focal plane of the lens.

Figure 6: Scheme of the experimental setups. (a) Young double slit interferometer and (b) Wollaston prism interferometer. In this scheme P , P_{45° and P_{90° are polarizers, Q is the sample waveplate placed on the motor M , L is a lens with a focal distance of $f = 25$ cm, and CL is a cylindrical lens of $f = 25$ mm. Each dotted region refers to the portion of the image for measuring Φ_{tilt} (green) and $\Phi_{\text{tilt}} + \Phi_m$ (blue).

When recording the additional shift produced by tilted or non-plane-parallel retarders, Φ_{tilt} , the last polarizer is placed between the double slit and Q . This removes the polarimetric effect of rotating it.

The other proposed experimental setup, based on a Wollaston prism, is represented in Fig. 6b. It consists of the same light source of $\lambda = 639$ nm and the polarizer oriented at 45° (P_{45°). Then, the Wollaston prism is followed by a linear polarized cut in half and oriented at 45° ($P_{45^\circ}^\alpha$) before the sample retarder (Q) mounted at the motor (M). After that, we placed a cylindrical lens (CL) is used so the two beams at the exit of the Wollaston prism merge spatially. Also, by adjusting the distance from the lens to the camera, the period of the interference fringes can be varied. Finally, another polarizer cut in half and complementary to the first one, also oriented at 45° ($P_{45^\circ}^\beta$), is set before the camera. The cut polarizers are used to record at the same time the fringe displacement due to tilted or non-plane-parallel retarders and the characterization experiment, the top part is used to characterize Φ_{tilt} , while using the bottom part $\Phi_m + \Phi_{\text{tilt}}$ is measured.

Both setups accomplish the aim of obtaining a more compact and stabilized system. The Young interferometer was the first approach we analyzed and we checked that fluctuations due to pressure, temperature and wavelength changes are eliminated. The Wollaston interferometer also fulfills this requirement and allowed to significantly decrease the size of the setup, leading to a more compact device. Also, Wollaston interferometer allowed us

to determine Φ_{tilt} and Φ_m with a single measurement instead of two like with the Young interferometer. The interference pattern corresponding to each setup is also represented in Fig. 6. The images of these patterns are collected and post-processed as the sum all values in each column to obtain a 1D intensity profile for that retarder rotation angle, $I(\theta)$. In the case of the Young interferometer, the power needs to be controlled using polarizer P to avoid saturating the camera, while this is not necessary for Wollaston interferometer, as the intensity is not focused in the y dimension. In the case of the Wollaston interferometer, this is performed independently for each half of the image avoiding the central region dominated by diffraction of $P_{45^\circ}^\alpha$ and $P_{45^\circ}^\beta$ polarizer borders. From the obtained intensity profiles, it is possible to calculate the spatial displacement of the fringes, Δx . We used two different algorithms to calculate the fringe displacement. The first method consists on calculating the correlation between $I(\theta)$ and $I(0)$. The position of the central peak is Δx and the distance between peaks is the period, d . Then, $\Phi = 2\pi\Delta x/d$. The second consists on calculating the fast Fourier transform (FFT) of $I(\theta)$, filtering the first order, calculating its inverse FFT and then calculating Φ as the mean complex phase of the retrieved signal. We did this for both measurements, $\Phi_1 = \Phi_{\text{tilt}}$ and $\Phi_2 = \Phi_{\text{tilt}} + \Phi_m$. Then, $\Phi_m = \Phi_2 + \Phi_1$. Finally, we fit Φ_m to Eq. 1 with Δ , θ_0 and Φ_0 to calculate their values. Fit parameter error is calculated using the procedure described in [22].

Figure 7 shows the experimental setups of the the schematics depicted in Fig. 6. From these images it is possible to appreciate a considerable different size from the double slit to the Wollaston prism, being the latter much more compact. The light source is a laser diode (MC6320CPWR-004S, Monocrom). Young interferometer setup used two different types of linear polarizers: thin film Thorlabs LPVISE-100A for $P_{45^\circ}^\alpha$ and $P_{45^\circ}^\beta$, and dichroic plastic Itos HN32 for the slits (P_0 and P_{90}) as they are easily cut. The double slit is composed of two slits of $160 \mu\text{m}$ width separated $730 \mu\text{m}$. A lens of $f = 25 \text{ cm}$ is used so the main diffraction lobe fills the width of the camera. Wollaston interferometer also used Thorlabs LPVISE-100A for P_{45° and dichroic plastic Itos HN32 polarizers for $P_{45^\circ}^\alpha$ and $P_{45^\circ}^\beta$, a Thorlabs WPQ10 wollaston prism with a separation angle between beams of $\approx 1^\circ$ and a cylindrical lens of $f = 25 \text{ mm}$. In both cases, the intensity images are recorded using a UI-1492LE-M μEye camera chip. The sample retarder is placed on a motorized rotary stages (X-RSW60A-E03, Zaber). Sample retarders are mounted in the motor without considering the position of the fast axis respect to the motor reference system, so θ_0 is random. In all cases, we recorded 361 intensity patterns from 0 to 360° in the motor reference system.

Figure 7: Experimental setups. (a) Based on a double slit with 0 - 90 linear polarizers. (b) Based on a Wollaston prism.

Figure 8: Experimental results of phase displacement for (a) WPQ10M-808 and (b) WPQ10E-405 calculated using the Wollaston interferometer and FFT processing and their residuals.

4. Experimental results

4.1. Optical retarders measurements

We characterized several retarders using both interferometers. The retarders under test were several zero-order quarter- and half-waveplates for different wavelengths, Table 1, shows the characterization several retarders with different Δ values at 639 nm, not only 90° and 180°. As an example, Fig. 8 shows the experimental and fit $\Phi_m(\theta)$ values for WPQ10M-808 and WPQ10E-405 ($\Delta \approx 120^\circ$ and $\Delta \approx 45^\circ$ for the illumination wavelength respectively) measured using Wollaston interferometer and with $\Phi_i(\theta)$ calculated using the FFT procedure. In general, all curves show small deviations from Eq. 1 and the fit parameter errors are low. However, the experimental values for the two maxima are slightly different, and the same occurs for the two minima. This might be due to a small error in the determination of Φ_{tilt} along with errors in the determination of Φ_2 . For this reason, we chose to determine Δ and θ_0 using nonlinear fits instead of using maximum and minimum values. Fig. 8 also shows the residuals of the fits. Their standard deviations are $\sigma_{\text{WPQ10M-808}} = 3.91^\circ$ and $\sigma_{\text{WPQ10E-405}} = 2.25^\circ$. The time for processing one sample, starting from the intensity profile until obtaining the phase displacement is around 50 ms.

Table 1 shows the results obtained for Δ using both the Young double slit and the Wollaston interferometer, and using correlation and FFT algorithms. It also shows the average fit error. For the Wollaston interferometer, we repeated each measurement 19 times varying the starting motor angle to artificially vary the retarder azimuth a controlled amount. This

allowed us to calculate the repeatability standard deviation. FFT algorithm shows equal or lower errors than correlation algorithm, so it is more accurate. We also calculated Δ_{nom} , the extrapolated retardance for our operating wavelength obtained with the information provided by the manufacturer at 632.8 nm. Finally, we measured the Mueller matrix for the retarders and extracted its retardance from it to compare our results to others obtained using a different non-interferometric method [23]. The retardance calculated from Mueller matrix polarimetry is expected to present a higher error as it is a more general method to characterize any polarization optical element. The results between both methods are coherent. Nevertheless, the WPL225H-632.8 retarder shows a much greater deviation from its nominal and Mueller polarimetry retardance value. This shows that our method presents lower precision for retardances near 180° due to the low visibility of the fringes pattern for many rotation angles and the big variations in Φ precisely at those angles. See Figure 4. We also calculated the azimuth with its error for all retarders. The maximum scale of its standard deviation error is about 0.23° .

Optical sample	Δ_{nom} ($^\circ$)	Young double slit		Wollaston prism		Mueller
		Δ ($^\circ$)		Δ ($^\circ$)		Δ ($^\circ$)
Model	@ 639 nm n constant	Correlation	FFT	Correlation	FFT	-
WPQ10M-808	116.35	112.04	112.76	117.07	117.67	118.05
WPH10M-808	233.21	231.55	231.12	232.33	231.69	234.66
WPQ10E-405	51.02	41.97	42.27	46.77	46.23	44.96
WPQ10ME-830	120.23	112.19	112.8	116.14	115.94	116.17
WPQ10ME-633	90.20	90.30	90.92	91.83	90.00	91.66
WPL225H-632.8	179.38	167.13	165.96	165.42	163.60	177.53
Fit error ($^\circ$)	—	0.083	0.091	0.080	0.057	0.86
Repeat. std ($^\circ$)	—	—	—	1.2	0.27	—

Table 1: Nominal and experimental retardance Δ of the retarder for different interferometric methods. The model name indicates whether it is a half waveplate (WPH or WPL225H-632.8) or a quarter waveplate (WPQ). The nominal retardance is calculated for a wavelength of $\lambda = 639$ nm. We did not perform repeatability measurements for Young double slit either for Mueller. The Mueller fit error was calculated in a different way from interferometric measurements.

does

4.2. Liquid crystal measurement

We also characterized a liquid crystal variable retarder (LCC-1223A, Thorlabs) using the Wollaston interferometer and the FFT algorithm, as it is the most accurate configuration and algorithm. This liquid crystal behaves as a linear retarder whose retardance depends on a voltage applied to it. This allowed us characterizing retarders with different retardance and the same azimuth by varying the applied voltage. For comparison, we

also characterized it using Mueller polarimetry [23]. Fig. 9a shows the retardance obtained using both methods and the values provided by the supplier. We noticed the existence of three differentiated regions. These are limited by the wrapping behavior of the retardance because only values from 0° to 180° present different Jones or Mueller matrices. However, it is possible to experimentally measure the retardances outside these bounds and they manifest as alternating discontinuities in Δ and θ_0 . To invert this phenomena and obtain Fig. 9, we applied [24]:

$$\begin{aligned} N_{even} & : \quad \Delta = \Delta' + N\pi & \theta_0 = \theta'_0, \\ N_{odd} & : \quad \Delta = 2\pi - \Delta' + (N - 1)\pi & \theta_0 = \theta'_0 - \frac{\pi}{2}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where Δ' and θ'_0 are the values directly measured. Thus, we observe that the results from the interferometric method and Mueller polarimetry agree very well for voltages ≥ 1 V and is closer to the supplier data for lower voltages. This mismatching may be due to different temperature conditions that modified the liquid crystal behavior as Mueller and interferometric experiments were separated by one year. We also calculated from our measurements the mean value of the azimuth fast axis, which resulted $\bar{\theta} = 12.7^\circ \pm 3.7^\circ$. For the calculation of this value, we also considered the experimental results near to the previously mentioned discontinuities. This could have led to an increase of the error. For a more in-depth characterization of the liquid crystal, we carried out another experiment to observe the effects of a changing retardance. We maintained the same angular position of $\theta = \theta_0$ and varied the applied voltage in steps of 0.25 V. We collected images for all voltages and we correlated all of them to obtain a graphical description of the fringes displacements. Fig. 9b shows the fringes displacement for different values of retardance. As we expected from Eq. 1 when considering $\theta = \theta_0$, we obtained a unitary negative slope linear behavior. Hence, there is a displacement of the fringes to the left when increasing the retardance.

5. Conclusions

In this work, we present two devices for the characterization of optical retarders based on a Young double slit and a Wollaston prism interferometers. They present advantages over previous devices since they are more stable, as they are common-path interferometers. In addition, they improve the accuracy in the experimental results. Among them, we have preferred the Wollaston interferometer because is simpler and more compact (over 25 cm in length). We have simulated and studied the effects and tolerances of the interferometers when varying the parameters of the composing optical elements. Also, the two physical devices have been assembled and a calibration procedure for subtracting the offset of the measurements have been developed for both setups. Finally, we experimentally measured several optical retarders and a liquid crystal with variable voltage. The measurements were

Figure 9: (a) Experimental results obtained with Wollaston interferometer (blue dots) are compared to those obtained with a Mueller polarimeter (green crosses) and to the data provided by Thorlabs (red line) and the residuals between Wollaston and Mueller measurements. (b) Displacement of the fringes in terms of the liquid crystal retardance for the Wollaston set-up and unitary negative slope linear fitting.

compared to Mueller polarimetry, showing a good agreement, presenting an uncertainty of the order of 0.1° for the retardance and 0.4° for the azimuth.

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